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RESEARCH ON COMBUSTION BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID COMPOSITE BY FIRE DYNAMICS SIMULATOR

Changwon National University
Park Yoon Hee

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Necessity

Recently, composite materials have been used in various fields such as construction and aviation, **which require improved flame retardancy**. However, it is disadvantageous that large structures are costly and time consuming to perform these experiments.

Objective

In this study, fire model of **Composites** is investigated by analyzing the behavior of heat release rate generated in the event of fire using the Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) based on CFD.

FDS (Fire Dynamics Simulator)

- Simulation program developed by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).
- Computer Fluid Dynamics (CFD) Fire Models Using LES

Pyrosim

- Fire investigation simulation program based on FDS
- Easy to implement complex modeling

Cone Calorimeter Test

- Heat Release Rate (HRR) measurement using Cone Calorimeter (FFT, England)
- 100(mm)x100(mm) maximum thickness of 50(mm) can be measured
- Test carried out in accordance with ISO5660-1, ASTM E-1354.

FDS combustion model

- Actual fire conditions: substances released depending on the material with heat release

➔ Mathematical interpretation of this is necessary

- Material Properties: Measure and apply using DSC and TGA equipment
- Sample Size : 100(mm)x100(mm)x4.3(mm)
- Test Environment: 25.0°C, 99.6 kPa

$$(2) v_S = \frac{W_F}{W_S} y_S ; W_S = X_H H_H + (1 - X_H) W_C$$

$$(3) v_{CO} = \frac{W_F}{W_{CO}} y_{CO}$$

compartment mesh setting

$$D^* = \left[\frac{Q^*}{\rho_\infty C_p T_\infty \sqrt{g}} \right]$$

D^* : Characteristic fire diameter

ρ_∞ : ambient air density

C_p : ambient air specific heat

T_∞ : ambient air temperature

g : Gravity acceleration

Q^* : heat release rate

Comparing Results

- Using theoretical equations, it is impossible to apply changes in the **actual environment and chemical composition**
- The combustion behavior is similar since the material is applied under the precondition that the material's fuel burn remains unchanged, but the **shape of the combustion behavior is similar**
- **Accurate environment and material properties** are required to reduce errors
- **Factors affecting ignition time** : thermal conductivity, density, ignition surface temperature, ambient temperature, radiation rate, radiation rate

Future Work

Thank you for attention